

Study of Fingerprint Patterns in Relation to Different Blood Groups Among the Students of FAAMC, Barpeta by Using 10 Finger Attributes**Jayasri Devi¹, Priyankita Nath², Santanu Kumar Sarma³, Tribeni Medhi⁴, Swapna D Kakoty⁵**¹Professor & Head, Department of Anatomy, Fakhruddin Ali Ahmed Medical College, Barpeta, Assam, India²Assistant Professor, Department of Anatomy, MGM Medical college, Navi Mumbai, Maharashtra, India³Assistant Professor, Department of Anatomy, FAAMC, Barpeta, Assam, India⁴Associate Professor, Department of Anatomy, FAAMC, Barpeta, Assam, India⁵Professor & Head, Department of Community Medicine, FAAMC, Barpeta, Assam, India

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Abstract

Fingerprints and dermal ridge pattern are unique with each individual. Even fingerprints are different between similar twins also. The fingerprints of both hands are not the same. Fingerprints do not change size or shape throughout a person's life, except in cases of serious injuries that scar the dermis. Therefore our objective to study the patterns of finger print among the students of FAAMC, Barpeta in relation to blood groups by using 10 finger attributes. After analysis the present study reveals that there is significant association between different fingerprint patterns in ABO blood group. In our study the commonest fingerprint pattern observed was whorls followed by loops and then arches. Whereas in Rh +ve blood group same findings were observed but in Rh -ve blood group only loops were recorded. This study is an attempt to associate fingerprints with different blood groups and Rh blood types which will enhance the authenticity of fingerprints in identification in forensic medicine. Hence we can strive to use the study to link fingerprints with blood types which can augment the accuracy of fingerprints in recognition and revelation of culprit and help in forensic medicine to identify the victim.

Keywords: Fingerprints, Pattern, Blood group, Relation, Significant.

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Introduction

Fingerprint is one of human body's most significant accurate special characteristics tool for personal identification of human being[1,2]. The word dermatoglyphics comes from two Greek words (*derma* means skin and *glyph* meaning carve) and refers to the friction ridge formations which appear on the palms of the hands and soles of the feet. Dermatoglyphics is the scientific study of fingerprints, lines, mounts, and shapes of hands. Dermatoglyphics refers to the formation of naturally occurring ridges on certain body parts, namely palms, fingers, soles and toes. The term dermatoglyphics was coined by Dr. Harold Cummins[3], the father of American fingerprint analysis, even though the process of fingerprint identification had already been used for several hundred years. Sir Francis Galton 1892[4], conducted extensive research on the importance of skin-ridge patterns, demonstrating their permanence and identification in his book Fingerprints.

Fingerprints and dermal ridge pattern are unique with each individual. Even Fingerprints are different between similar twins also. Fingerprints are usually developed during the 12th to 20th week of intrauterine life[5]. The fingerprints of both hands are not the same. The classification and uses of fingerprints, which marked the beginning of the modern era of fingerprint identification and is the basis for other classification systems. In 1929, Harold Cummins[1] and Charles Midlo M.D., together with others, published the influential book Fingerprints, Palms and Soles, a bible in the field of dermatoglyphics. Fingerprints do not change size or shape throughout a person's life, except in cases of serious injuries that scar the dermis. The significant ABO blood group system was discovered by Austrian Scientist Karl Landsteiner in 1900[6]. It consists of 'ABO' and 'Rhesus' groups. 'ABO' is further subdivided into A, B, AB and O blood group types and 'Rhesus' system is further subdivide into Rhesus positive(Rh +ve) and

Rhesus negative(Rh -ve). Study done by some researchers found relation between different blood groups with different pattern of finger prints [7,8,9]. Therefore our objective is to study the patterns of finger print among the students of FAAMC, Barpeta in relation to blood groups by using 10 finger attributes.

Materials and Methods

The study was carried out in Fakhruddin Ali Ahmed Medical, Barpeta. 200 medical students were selected of age group 18-25 from 1st and 2nd year for the study(excluding anatomical abnormalities or injuries of the finger) out of which 100 males and 100 females. Written informed consent was taken from all the students and Ethical clearance was obtained from Institutional Ethics Committee. The procedure was explained to the students and asked them to clean both the hands

before taking fingerprints. Finger prints were taken using the violet stamp pad of Supreme Delux Company size 96 X 160mm. Participant age, name, sex and blood groups were recorded in predesigned proforma having serial number. ABO blood group and Rh typing of the students were recorded from their identity card. Fingerprints of all the ten fingers (Fig 1) were taken on the respective blank paper where serial numbers were given by ink method as suggested by Cummins[3].The fingerprints were studied by using magnifying hand lens and identified as Arches, Loops, Whorls as stated by Galton[4] and recorded in tabulated form.

Data collected were tabulated under the headings of Male, Female, ABO and Rh blood group. Study design employed was Chisquare (χ^2) test to compare variables and tests will be considered significant when P value < 0.05.

Figure 1: Finger prints of ten fingers of a student

Results

Total 200 students were selected for study. Among 200 students, 100 were male and 100 were female. In Table 1, distribution of blood groups in male majority belonged to ‘O’(36%) followed by ‘B’(32%), ‘A’(28%) and ‘AB’(4%) but in female Table:1 showed majority belonged to ‘B’(44%) followed by ‘O’(28%), ‘A’(26%) and ‘AB’(2%). In this study, among 200 students blood group ‘B’ was noted more common blood group. But in male it was noted that blood group ‘O’(36%) were more common whereas in female blood group ‘B’(44%) were more common. Highly significant association(i.e., $p < 0.05$) between blood group and

gender among the students were recorded(Table 1). In Table 2, regarding Rhesus factor in relation to gender in male(Fig 2) Rh+ve recorded highest in ‘O’(34%), followed by ‘A’ (28%) and ‘B’ (28%) and ‘AB’ (4%) blood group. Whereas Rh-ve recorded only in ‘B’ (4%) and in ‘O’ (2%) blood group.

But in female (Fig 3) Rh+ve recorded highest in ‘B’(42%), followed by ‘O’ (28%) and ‘A’ (26%) and ‘AB’ (2%) blood group. Whereas Rh-ve blood group recorded only in ‘B’ (2%) blood group. Among 200 students Total Rh+ve blood group recorded 96% (Table 2) against Rh-ve blood group recorded only 4%(Table 2).

Table 1: Distribution of ABO blood group in relation to gender

Gender	Blood Group				Total
	A(%)	B(%)	AB(%)	O(%)	
Male	28(28%)	32(32%)	4 (4%)	36(36%)	100
Female	26(26%)	44(44%)	2 (2%)	28(28%)	100
Total	54(27%)	76(38%)	6 (3%)	64(32%)	200
Chi-square test	16.9				
P-Value	0.000686				
Statistical significance at 5% level	Significant				

Table 2: Distribution of ABO blood group and Rhesus factor in relation to gender

Gender	Blood group (%)								
	A+ve (%)	A-ve (%)	B+ve (%)	B-ve (%)	AB+ve (%)	AB-ve (%)	O+ve (%)	O-ve (%)	Total
Male	28 (28%)	0 (0%)	28 (28%)	4 (4%)	4 (4%)	0 (0%)	34 (34%)	2 (2%)	100
Female	26 (26%)	0 (0%)	42 (42%)	2 (2%)	2 (2%)	0 (0%)	28 (28%)	0 (0%)	100
Total	(27%)	(0%)	(35%)	(3%)	(3%)	(0%)	(31%)	(1%)	200
Total (%) Rh +ve	96%								
Total (%) Rh -ve	4%								

Figure 2: Distribution of ABO blood group and Rh factor in male students

Figure 3: Distribution of ABO blood group and Rh factor in female students

In Table 3. Finger print pattern analysis showed that common pattern of finger print was whorl 824(41.2%) followed by loop 718(35.9%) and arch 458(22.9%). In present study regarding gender among the students whorls were recorded highest

(54.61%) in male whereas in female arches were recorded highest (56.76%). After statistical analysis (Chi-square value-14.672 and P<0.05) it was found that there is significant association between fingerprint patterns and gender (Table 3).

Table 3: Distribution of fingerprint patterns in relation to gender

Fingerprint patterns	Gender (%)		Total (%)
	Male (%)	Female (%)	
Arch	198 (43.23%)	260 (56.76%)	458 (22.9%)
Loop	352 (49.0%)	366 (50.97%)	718 (35.9%)
Whorl	450 (54.61%)	374 (45.38%)	824 (41.2%)
Total	1000	1000	2000
Chi-square test	14.672		
P- Value	0.000395		
Statistical significance at 5% level	Significant		

Figure 4: Arch

Figure 5: Loop

Figure 6: Whorl

During analysis of data in different fingerprint patterns in regards to ABO blood group (Table 4)

highest number of arches(33.18%) were found in 'B'(44.97%) followed by 'A'(33.18%),

‘O’(20.52%) and ‘AB’(1.31%) respectively. Loops were recorded highest in blood group ‘B’ (40.66%) followed by ‘O’ (28.69%), ‘A’ (27.85%) and ‘AB’ (2.78%). In Table 4, showed whorls were highest in blood group ‘B’ (41.50%) followed by ‘O’ (28.64%), ‘A’ (25.72%) and ‘AB’ (2.72%). In Table 4, it was noted that all the fingerprint patterns

were highest in ‘B’ (42.37%) and lowest in ‘AB’ (2.73%) blood group. In statistical analysis it was found (Table 4) that association between fingerprint patterns and ABO blood group was highly significant (Chi-square value-23.77 and $P < 0.05$).

Table 4: Distribution of fingerprint patterns in relation to ABO blood groups

Fingerprint patterns	Blood group (%)				Total
	A (%)	B (%)	AB (%)	O (%)	
Arch	152 (33.18%)	206 (44.97%)	6 (1.31%)	94(20.52%)	458
Loop	200 (27.85%)	292 (40.66%)	20 (2.78%)	206 (28.69%)	718
Whorl	212 (25.72%)	342 (41.50%)	34 (4.12%)	236 (28.64%)	824
Total	564(28.91%)	840(42.37%)	60 (2.73%)	494 (25.95%)	2000
Chi-square test	23.77				
P-Value	0.000554				
Statistical significance at 5% level	Significant				

Table 5: Distribution of fingerprint patterns in Rhesus blood groups

Fingerprint Patterns	Blood Group (%)		
	Rh+ve (%)	Rh-ve (%)	Total
Arch	458 (100%)	0.0 (0%)	458
Loop	712 (99.16%)	6 (0.83%)	718
Whorl	824 (100%)	0.0 (0%)	824
Total	1994(99.7%)	6(0.3%)	2000

In our study during analysis of different fingerprint patterns in respect to Rhesus factor (Table 5, Fig 7) whorls and arches were recorded highest (100%) whereas loops were recorded (99.16%) in Rh +ve blood group. In Rh-ve blood group the only fingerprint pattern that was observed was loop (0.83%, Table 5, Fig 7).

Figure 7: Distribution of different finger print patterns in regards to Rh factor

In Table 5 (Fig 7) comparison of different finger print patterns between Rhesus +ve and Rhesus -ve blood group, noted that arches and whorls were 100% whereas loops were 99.16% in Rh+ve blood group. On the other hand in Rh-ve blood group only 0.83% loops were recorded.

Discussion

Medical students of our study showed highest percentage of blood group ‘B’ followed by ‘O’, ‘A’ and ‘AB’ which was similar with the findings of previous researchers [10, 11]. In our study significant association (i.e., $p < 0.05$) between blood group and gender among the students were recorded. Same observation was reported by

Ranjan RK, Kataria DS, Perwaiz SA in 2015 [10]. Highest(96%) Rh+ve blood group recorded among 200 students against Rh-ve blood group(4%). Same observation was recorded by some researchers[12]. In our study (Table 4) it was recorded that commonest fingerprint pattern among all the ABO blood groups was whorl 824(41.2%) followed by loop 718(35.9%) and arch 458(22.9%) which was similar with the findings of Thakur A, Yadav J and Tiwari G[13] and contrary to the findings of Ray R K [18] and Deepa D[7] and Kshirsagar[21] who recorded highest number of fingerprint pattern loops(60.95%) followed by whorls(32.55%) and arches(6.5%) and Rastogi et.al.(Loop 60.95%, whorl 32.55% and arch 6.5%)[19]. But some researchers[10,14,15,16] found commonest fingerprint pattern was loop followed by whorl and arch. In this study among all the blood groups highest number of arches(Table 4) were observed in blood group 'B'(44.97%) followed by 'A'(33.18%), 'O'(20.52%) and 'AB'(1.31%) which corroborates with other researchers [10, 13]. Whereas in our study regarding loop highest numbers recorded in blood group 'B'(40.66%) followed by 'O'(28.69%), 'A'(27.85%) and 'AB'(2.78%), this finding is similar with some researchers[12,13,]. In present study Highest number of whorls were recorded in blood group 'B'(41.50%) followed by 'O'(28.64%), 'A'(25.72%) and 'AB'(2.73%) which is same with the findings of some researchers [10, 11, 13, 20]. Regarding different fingerprint patterns in relation to 'ABO' blood group, most commonest pattern was the whorl(41.2%) followed by loop(35.9%) and arch(22.9%), same observation was reported by Narayana et al[17,] and there was significant relation between 'ABO' blood group and different fingerprint patterns (Table 3, P value 0.000554).

Distribution of fingerprint patterns of medical students in our study revealed statistical significant association between fingerprint patterns and ABO blood group which is similar with other researchers [21].

Regarding Rh factor in ABO blood group our study showed that arches and whorls dominated (100%) over loops (99.16%) in Rh +ve medical students of FAA Medical College, Barpeta, Assam. But this findings did not match with observations of previous researchers [11,13,16] who noted that irrespective of the blood group, loop was the commonest fingerprint pattern followed by whorl and arches.

Conclusion

After analysis the present study reveals that there is significant association between different fingerprint patterns in ABO blood group. In our study the commonest fingerprint pattern observed was

whorls followed by loops and then arches. Whereas in Rh +ve blood group same findings were observed but in Rh -ve blood group only loops were recorded. There is further scope to study this patterns in medical students by other methods in more details. Fingerprints are unique for every individual and never change from birth till death. This study is an attempt to associate fingerprints with different blood groups and Rh blood types which will enhance the authenticity of fingerprints in identification in forensic medicine. Hence we can strive to use the study to link fingerprints with blood types which can augment the accuracy of fingerprints in recognition and revelation of culprit and help in forensic medicine to identify the victim.

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